

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-292-IC-2% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20230403
Vial:	101	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 292
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	270.0nm
Run Time:	25.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 270.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	4/3/2023 6:03:57 PM CST		
Date Processed:	4/4/2023 9:41:20 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	14.498	161684	33.09	7484
2	16.489	161704	33.09	6721
3	19.015	82097	16.80	2995
4	19.781	83128	17.01	2853

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-293-IC-2% ASY	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20230403
Vial:	102	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 293
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	270.0nm
Run Time:	25.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 270.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	4/3/2023 6:29:37 PM CST		
Date Processed:	4/4/2023 9:43:49 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	14.585	2154475	98.60	98694
2	16.512	2046	0.09	161
3	19.087	28206	1.29	1325
4	19.787	288	0.01	54